

Editorial

Redressing epistemic injustice in global health: harnessing community knowledge systems

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INTRODUCTION

Epistemology is a philosophical study of the origin, nature and limits of human knowledge. It is relevant to how we understand what knowledge is, types and synthesis of knowledge, and its impact over time [1]. There are discourses around whether and how the epistemic base can be diversified, and enriched by incorporating traditionally under-prioritized methods, regions, and specific populations (e.g. indigenous, and traditional practitioners) whose voices and experiences have been systematically excluded [2]. The conservative approach seems to have prescribed researchers to invest considerable resources in expounding epistemic base rooted in existing frameworks, methodologies, and theories, instead of co-developing these knowledge sanctuaries based on the local epistemologies, cultures and practices [3]. The repeated practice of submitting and espousing western ideologies and theories has been considered to engender unjust predominance of knowledge synthesis escalating marginalization of the local knowledge system and are increasingly discussed under the topic of 'decolonizing global health' and 'decolonization of philosophy' [4-6].

Recently the discourses on de-colonization and epistemic injustice have received increasing attention globally [5, 7, 8]. Notwithstanding this, the concentration of power and privilege among the scholars of HICs continue to create a difference in global health research to underestimate and exploit the scholarships and scholars from low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). While we as global health researchers aspire for a new shift in global health, it is essential to pay

attention to the reflexivity of such discourses, for instance who discusses it, why and for whom? More importantly, evaluating questions such as whether these discourses are serving LMIC scholars, if so in what ways are essential. Although these discourses remind global researchers to be vigilant of global health inequities, epistemic injustice embedded in paternalism, hegemony, racism and white saviorism, all could lead to a vicious cycle of injustice. The fact that they hold most power and privileges, recognized entity as power differentials, LMIC researchers simply could be in an inherently disadvantaged position to defend the Global Health structure and its functioning (e.g. funding arrangements, career related aspirations) that continue to favor new forms of exploitation [9]. One way to resolve this neo-exploitation and embrace the goals of knowledge decolonization is to submit and promote community knowledge system and experiential knowledge of LMIC scholars diversifying the lens of western epistemic theories and practices. Below, we discuss how epistemic justice could be achieved by harnessing community knowledge system.

Generating and applying knowledge is inherently complex due to its context-, historical-, cultural-, and community-specific nature. Yet, the overwhelming influx of literature often imposes generalized ideas on how particular communities should function, underestimating the values of pose and gaze in global health [10, 11]. Implementing a policy or an intervention overlooking the social and cultural relevance, undermining the community values may simply incur suspicion, resistance and failure. The recent examples of policy failures can be learnt from COVID-19

vaccine mandates which failed to receive widespread public acceptance [12] while at the same time, vaccine hoarding by high income countries failed to avail the vaccines in LMICs [13]—a reminder of injustice in global health.

Historically, policy translation and action towards its implementation has always remained inadequate and importantly have failed to reach the target population. In addition, health measures based on strategies driven by the facts and figures, and tenets underpinned by (western) science, while discounting the local knowledge held by communities has been underproductive and even counterproductive [14, 15]. Increased efforts towards understanding the community who are the immediate users are critical and require an approach without *a priori* assumption of western epistemic supremacy [4]. Some of the reasons for resistance to such community knowledge systems in indigenous and traditional societies particularly in LMICs are also underpinned by colonialism, neocolonialism and exploitations [16].

Neglect of community system of knowledge may disregard the values they possess. As a consequence of the past and current injustice, communities may simply place suspicion and distrust towards evidence based practice/interventions [16]. Such a gap between two sources of knowledge (evidence-based medicine/western science and community knowledge system) can only result to tension and discordance obviating the potential benefits that could have been reaped from their synergy [4, 17]. In fact, community epistemic system can be strengthened and blended with evidence

based medicine to harmonize the outcome, to secure and expand community buy in and ultimately improve its implementation [18].

At the same time, unless the engagement moves beyond the conventional methods of policy forums, engagement at high levels would simply produce impressive ‘paper tigers’ dissociating from the ground realities. The question then rises, who are these reports and scientific evidence targeting? How can they best serve the community? If they are intended for the community, it is essential to garner, foster and integrate the locally available knowledge and its system. Unless the local epistemic system and strategies are embraced, much of the policies and its implementation will suffer from poor uptake and community participation. If we invest in learning from our community based indigenous knowledge system while integrating the knowledge and insights from other epistemic resources [19], we can remediate the poor uptake and implementations that we see today.

One recent example of how an *a priori* assumption of biomedical intervention failed to operate can be learnt from the Ebola epidemic in Western Africa where community members distrusted health care workers’ scientific intention to isolate the Ebola affected corpse from their family members. Lack of or inconsistent consideration of community practices (washing the body of the deceased by the family members) without meaningfully engaging on how to incorporate new interventions significantly hampered public health efforts during the Ebola epidemic in Africa [20]. Researchers often impose linear prescriptions that undermine

cultural practices and familial traditions, which are intricately connected to the community's epistemic system. [21]. The Ebola outbreak clearly offers a valuable insight that community based epistemic system (in this case, their rituals) should be explored and weaved together with the proposed intervention, rather than vertically imposing how they should follow the science [22].

There is a strong push towards building community based epistemic system globally [4, 5, 23]. The systematic steps towards policy implementation can begin with formative research around existing community knowledge system that can inform the design of a policy and programme as opposed to imposing the intervention through 'distant science', foreign gaze, and policymakers' consensus [24]. Communities also tend to reject the policy and science imposed on them echoing with a wider trend of mistrust towards science in general. This mistrust in science is affecting the uptake of evidence around climate science, and recently (COVID-19) vaccines [17]. The conventional evidence based practice, policy and the agendas are often blinkered that simply overlooks the traditional and indigenous forms of knowledge that has been the way of their lives, that has offered respects to their living in harmony with the nature [25].

By harnessing community knowledge systems, community can benefit and bring in sustainable implementation practices that improves their health and living conditions. One such example is of Ladakh region in northern Himalayas where community based concept of ice-stupas have been proven to be

of immense value in mitigating the drought and reduced water supplies [26]. Similar to these practices, India has historical base of enormous knowledge system on how ancient community thrived to live healthy, in harmony with the nature through traditional Ayurvedic medicine, with some of the practices (e.g. Yoga, and meditation) currently being exported globally [27]. Indeed, such practices propound the nuggets for holistic living and spiritual dimension of health as embraced by WHO, and may bear solutions to the rising global mental health problems where allopathic care have its own limitations (adherence, prolonged duration and resistance) [28].

Same as how community practice for illnesses received attention later by scientific community leading to the adoption of quinine and Artesunate as antimalarials in saving millions of lives, there may be untapped potential in community epistemic system that remain under recognized, and underappreciated [23, 29]. There are several examples for community-based knowledge systems which have been serving millions of people since generations and are deemed beneficial for both the humans and the nature. For instance, Sherpas in Nepal make a unique worship to mountains, their customs, food and cultural practices and have always rendered mutual benefits for humans and the nature. Sherpas, the inhabitants of upper Himalayas practice '*Singi Nawa*' which literally means to ask someone before cutting any trees or woods. Timber forests take thousands of years to grow across the harsh Himalayan climate and are susceptible to degradation due to human activities. Indiscriminate cutting and logging will deplete these resources

beyond recovery. Through '*Singi Nawa*' the Sherpa elders have embraced conservation and community stewardship long before climate change became a central concern in global discourse.

The practice of '*Singi Nawa*' embodies an intuitive (self-sustainable) and culturally resonant approach to environmental conservation among Himalayan communities. In this system, a revered or respected person is asked before cutting trees in the community, such a community reverence system allows preservation of trees and nature without having to preach and patronize Sherpas using intricate scientific concepts which may be simply unconvincing for community members [30]. Such practices require increased attention and exploration through formative research to foster the epistemic diversity so that it could enhance community acceptability and in long run build interventions that are blended with the cultures [25].

Similar practices exist in most indigenous knowledge system across the globe, suggesting that indigenous population are often the most effective stewards of their own health and the environments in which they live [31]. In one study conducted in Amazon, deforestation rates were found to be 50% lower in areas protected by indigenous population compared to the rest [32]. And their rich community epistemic system also offers ways to live in harmony with nature, medicinal plants, envisioning their health as a concept of well-being embedded in self, family, community and the nature. The holistic concept of health and living similarly is embraced by the concept of '*ubuntu*' in

Southern Africa, which endorses how the health and happiness of one is inextricably linked to the other human beings [33]. The culture of *ubuntu* embraces caring of others as much as self, and stands in contrast to western tenet of 'autonomy'—individualistic wills for happiness and achievement alone [34]. The holistic living, and harmony with nature embraced by Indigenous health practice has been shown to have substantial opportunity for reducing the syndemic nature of chronic diseases and climate change whilst increasing food security and enhancing biodiversity across the world [35].

Increasingly in recent literature, decolonizing in global health has brought significant attention to existing power asymmetries in global knowledge production and dissemination but it insufficiently lays out how 'decolonisation' can be operationalized including the safeguarding of millions of people; whose traditional knowledge or value systems are on the verge of collapse. These discourses have not gone beyond the paywalls and institutions in high income countries, significantly limiting reach to local communities and institutions. Communities and local institutions—the true sources of local epistemic bases are incognizant and disconnected from the western epistemic forums and platforms shielded by the 'firey' paywalls of high-income country publishers and topics that primarily serves the 'gaze' of western institutions. Co-creation of knowledge can be a powerful tool, yet inadequately explored in academic global health, simply because this demands a radical shift in who, how, for whom the knowledge is created and demands equal ownership. While doing so, inherent power dynamics between knowledge

co-producers must be identified and thoroughly discussed and actively addressed throughout the process. These changes require a fundamental shift in epistemic system to allow a bi-directional flow of knowledge (for example, equal exchange between the community members and trained scholars) to ensure that knowledge is not hierarchized, rather harmonized. Engaging local communities as knowledge producers will truly foster effective collaboration and take us one step further in addressing some of the challenges the world is facing today (2).

CONCLUSIONS

Epistemic supremacy, fomented by colonial and neocolonial injustices rendered over centuries, has relegated indigenous knowledge systems especially in LMICs. Empowering communities, building capacity to employ indigenous gaze/pose is an immediate first step which can occur with co-creation, and engagement in global health practice. It is essential to move past the regular western epistemic base and consider building (local) community epistemic system for culturally sensitive approaches to designing and implementing health policies and practices.

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